

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Amegassi****FIRST NAME: Gottlieb****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft office 365 on macOS 11.1 (20C69)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)
3. Eleven (11) Important Reminders (EUCLID 2019, 17-18)
4. When should a number be written out, and when should a numeral be used? (EUCLID 2019, 21-22)
5. What is a Style Guide, and Why Would I Need One? (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
6. "Equality" Vocabulary (EUCLID 2019, 32)
7. Quotations (EUCLID 2019, 48-49)

WRITE TITLE GIVEN TO RP

1) INTRODUCTION

Like a doe that sighs beside the water, I could not wait to discover the first course of my doctoral cycle. While engaging in this course, many questions aroused in my mind. The main interrogations were: What is the rationale of this course? What new rules and techniques will I learn? How do they relate to my thesis project? Why is it compulsory rather than optional? In a nutshell, does it worth the investment?

Bearing all those questions in mind, I began the journey. First, I went through the assigned material (ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1) as well as the recommended videotape (related to the correct use of the software Zotero) available on the Learning Management System (LMS) platform. Then, as I was looking for insights and evidence that could help answer my initial questions, I read the coursepack with purpose as suggested by Cleenewerck and Gulma (EUCLID 2019, 2) and discovered some interesting concepts.

The purpose of the current response paper is to share my thoughts on some of the key concepts that I have learned from the readings.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The American English language online dictionary, Merriam-Webster, defines the word essay as “an analytic or interpretative literary composition usually dealing with its subject from a limited or personal point of view” (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). As we generally write an essay to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence (EUCLID 2019, 1), we should pay particular attention to the text’s quality. For example, in “The Art of poetry,” the author recommends to “observe the language well in all you write” (Nicolas Boileau Despréaux 1683, 10). Indeed, in the professional world, especially in research activities, quality writing contributes to fostering the author’s credibility vis-à-vis his stakeholders. Conversely, a low-quality paper could raise questions about its author’s expertise, rigor, and credibility. Thus, I believe it would be advantageous for every aspiring writer to follow the basics of writing an essay as suggested in the coursepack. According to this material, a good essay should have a thesis statement and argument. That thesis should be developed “via a set of closely related points by reasoning and evidence” (EUCLID 2019, 1). It is also important to base arguments on robust foundations, especially in academic essays. A common way of fostering trust writings is by “supporting evidence and information from academic texts or credible sources” (EUCLID 2019, 1). That said, what if the topic is not stated in an interrogative form? What if the researcher explores a brand-new domain of interest with no or very few academic papers available to support her/his thesis? What other tools can the researcher use to foster her/his paper’s credibility despite the lack of abundant references? As I have not yet found precise answers to these few questions that arose when studying the essay writing chapter, it could be a great idea to examine them in another article.

3) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

“Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers,” it is not common to see this title attributed to a text, and this is what hooked me. Indeed, first, I was intrigued by the title of this chapter as it seemed atypical to me. Then, curiosity led me to read it with the intent of discovering. Finally, I found it interesting and started reading this section of the coursepack with purpose. As a result, I have noticed a dramatic improvement in the quality of my professional writings. Most refinements were in terms of clarity, stylistic variety, and focusing.

Rules developed in this chapter seem trivial, but in my opinion, they are of utmost importance. I appreciate the “do” and “do not” format as it knocks to the point, and the ideas developed are practical. It inspires me the idea of setting up a personal checklist of best practices related to professional writing. Advice like “when you finish writing, read your paper out loud. Writing that does not sound right will not read right” (EUCLID 2019, 16) are they are easy to implement while having very positive outcomes on the paper’s quality. I also positively appreciated the attention point related to the balance to find between the need for supporting information from credible sources and the constraint of not submitting a paper that strings together lots of quotations (EUCLID 2019, 15).

The recommendation related to using the first person singular in this document (EUCLID 2019, 16) seems a little controversial. Indeed, I still miss a clear understanding of the rationale behind using the first person singular in academic writing.

One in the other, this session of the coursepack has fully satisfied my expectations by its easy-to-read format, the practical nature of the advice, and their positive effects on the learner's paper quality. As a result, the statement: "small investments of time can produce important results" (EUCLID 2019, 16) has a particular resonance in my mind.

4) LITERATURE REVIEW

In a contribution entitled "The Literature Review: A Few Tips On Conducting It," published on the website of the University of Toronto, Dena Taylor stated that "a literature review is an account of what has been published on a topic by accredited scholars and researchers" (Taylor 2021). The essay guide resource: "What is a literature review?", supports the idea that "a literature review shows your readers that you have an in-depth grasp of your subject; and that you understand where your own research fits into and adds to an existing body of agreed knowledge" (The Royal Literature Fund, n.d.). In the following lines, we will explore some reminders (EUCLID 2019, 17-18) and writing instructions (EUCLID 2019, 21-22) related to the literature review.

a) Eleven (11) Important Reminders

In my opinion, the reminders at the beginning of this sub-section are handy. They help to recall some rules and learn some new ones. First, the concept of restrictive and non-restrictive phrases (EUCLID 2019, 17) was not very clear in my mind. With the help of some additional readings (mainly a blog post on the website "grammarly.com" and the institutional website of Walden University), I better understood the theoretical concept that I already use to apply in my writings. When writing, the correct use of punctuation is of utmost importance and can make a big difference. Indeed, punctuations can be very confusing, especially if you do not know where to place them. Depending on the position of punctuations, the entire meaning of a sentence can change. The following examples taken from the website "digitalsynopsis.com" are good illustrations of the importance of punctuations.

Example 1: "Let's eat Grandma" instead of "Let's eat, Grandma."

Example 2: "I'm sorry I love you" instead of "I'm sorry; I love you."

In a nutshell, in my opinion, this section reminding some important rules about punctuation is a great idea.

b) When should a Number be Written out, and when should a Numeral be Used?

According to the online dictionary Merriam-Webster, a number can be characterized as a unit belonging to an abstract mathematical system and subject to specified laws of succession, addition, and multiplication. It is generally used to count, measure and label. There arises the question of when should a number be written out and when should a numeral be used?

From my readings, I understand that rules are not standardized and depend a lot on the style you are applying. In the Turabian and Chicago Manual Style (CMS) guide for American English, “generally, numbers should be written as numerals (i.e., 8, 45, 1001), especially in writing where numbers frequently occur” (EUCLID 2019, 21). I have also learned that one should always spell out numbers when they begin a sentence, no matter how large or small. This rule is also applicable to numbers like “second” and “tenth.” Conversely, according to an article published on the website Scribendi.com “decimals are always written as numerals for clarity and accuracy” (Scribendi Inc, n.d.).

That said, in the section as mentioned earlier, related to numbers, I do not understand why the author chose to talk about adjectives & adverbs (e.g., good/well) or the use of singular or plural.

5) WHAT IS A STYLE GUIDE, AND WHY WOULD I NEED ONE?

According to Wikipedia, “a style guide, or style manual, is a set of standards for the writing and design of documents, either for general use or for a specific publication, organization or field. The implementation of a style guide provides uniformity in style and formatting within a document and across multiple documents” (List of Style Guides 2021). A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to some aspects of writing style that need to be consistent (EUCLID 2019, 24).

Depending on the academic discipline, the professional body, the school, etc., there are several style guides. “The three most frequently used style guides are the publication manual of the American Psychological Association (APA), the Modern Language Association’s MLA Style Manual, and the Chicago Manual of Style (CMOS)” (Cambridge Proofreading LLC 2019).

One thing I most appreciated in Euclid’s coursepack is the balanced approach of the authors, who invites the learners to visit more sources of information (mainly websites) that could help answer specific questions concerning style guides (EUCLID 2019, 25).

The website SCRIBBR precise that Turabian style is a version of Chicago style explicitly designed for students and researchers. It follows most Chicago conventions and

adds extra guidelines for formatting research papers, theses, and dissertations (Scribbr, n.d.).

Reasons for adopting a style guide are numerous. For the authors of the blogpost writethedocs.org, “it helps maintain a consistent style, voice, and tone across your documentation, whether you’re a lone writer or part of a huge docs team” (writethedocs.org 2019). In other words, a style guide is a set of standards to follow when writing a document. It ensures uniformity and consistency. It also helps your readers to understand your meaning.

6) “EQUALITY” VOCABULARY

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights states in its article 1 that: “all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood.” Article 7 of this same Declaration indicates that “all are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to equal protection of the law. All are entitled to equal protection against any discrimination in violation of this Declaration and against any incitement to such discrimination” (United Nations 1948).

The online Cambridge Dictionary defines equality as “the right of different groups of people to have a similar social position and receive the same treatment” (Cambridge dictionary 2021). It is also “a situation in which men and women, people of different races, religions, etc., are all treated fairly and have the same opportunities.” The UNICEF believes that “equal rights and opportunities for girls and boys help all children fulfill their potential” (UNICEF 2021). Likewise, according to the UN: “gender equality, besides being a fundamental human right, is essential to achieve peaceful societies, with full human potential and sustainable development. Moreover, it has been shown that empowering women spurs productivity and economic growth” (United Nations 2021).

From the above, we conclude that equality is essential for better inclusion and lasting peace. A change in behavior is, therefore, necessary for the sustainable development of our societies. One aspect of this virtuous change we call for is the use of an “equality” vocabulary. Words like “firefighter” instead of “fireman,” “police officer” instead of “policeman” and “salesperson” instead of “salesman” are concrete examples of “equality” vocabulary (EUCLID 2019, 32).

Let us be conscious of the weight of our words, let’s choose them with wisdom and care.

7) QUOTATIONS

Experts locate the origin of the word “quotation” around the late 16th century. It is said to derive from medieval Latin “quotationem.” According to one of the definitions proposed by Oxford Languages, the world’s leading dictionary publisher, a quotation is “a

group of words taken from a text or speech and repeated by someone other than the original author or speaker” (Oxford Languages 2021).

“Quotations must be placed in quotation marks or indented as a block quote. All quotations must include a citation, a note or parenthetical citation, referring the reader to the source document. As a matter of form, quotations should flow with your text and may be edited to do so” (EUCLID 2019, 48).

“When you quote, you include the words and ideas of others in your text exactly as they have expressed them” (Lane 2020). When quoting, it sometimes happens that one finds errors in the original text; there arises the dilemma of whether the writer should correct the error (and take the risk of distorting the initial thought of the author) or leave the text as such (and submit a document with mistakes). Fortunately, there is a solution offered to the writer for correcting errors. “For an unusual word choice, concept, term, or spelling it may be appropriate to emphasize the original is being quoted faithfully. This is done by inserting the Latin term *sic* (thus), in italics or underlined, and in brackets within the quotation (but in parentheses at the end of a quote), immediately following the term” (EUCLID 2019, 48).

8) CONCLUSION

I take special pride in writing these concluding words on this first tryout. Indeed, with the health crisis linked to Covid-19 and its socio-economic consequences, challenges have not been lacking; despite the turmoil, we got there with calm, determination, and consistency. From the start (through watching Prof. Cleenewerck’s instructional videos) to finish (last page of ACA-401 / ACA-401D Coursepack), this course will have kept me going.

I was a bit surprised that some links to websites recommended in the Initial student orientation 2020 were no longer functional (e.g., Questia (<https://www.questia.com/site-sunset>) that has ceased operations as of Monday, December 21, 2020, with individual subscriptions no longer available) and because of some minor typos such as “stident” (EUCLID 2020, 4) instead of “student.” However, overall, I came away enriched academically and personally from this incredible experience. I found answers to my initial questions relating to the rationale of this course and its value. In addition, I now have a better understanding of guide styles, citation rules, etc. In short, this first course in my doctoral program allowed me to write my professional and academic documents with more than assurance and serenity.

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